

Document Management System

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ABSTRACT

Document management has been an important component of organizations and institutes where mass work-forces are there. Storage, maintenance, updating and retrieval of documents becomes difficult as the amount of data gets larger with time. The data when stored in a digital format lacks authenticity and thereby compromising security at a large scale.

Thus, as a technological solution for this problem, this project comes with efficient management methods. An ideal software should fill the gap between security and efficiency.

The data should be available in desired time units and to all the intended users.

This project is an attempt of solving all the problems in a software meant for an institute (educational institute). The features include digital storage, retrieval using dynamic QR codes and digital attestation make the system usable and convenient to use. The project includes all the should be aspects of an ideal system for managing documents and simultaneously following the security constraints.

Keywords: Document, security, User, OTP

I. INTRODUCTION:

Nowadays, organizations or institutes ask for various documents to candidates who wish to enrolls, for validation at the time of admission, the institute may feel the need of producing the documents after frequent intervals. Also, the user is sometimes asked for producing documents for different activities and admission to other institutes. Carrying physical documents with proper or valid attestation becomes a

tedious ask when the number of documents increase. In some cases, the signature for attestation may be invalid causing a fraud also retrieval of physically stored documents is difficult that involve on paper trans- actions causing delay in obtaining the documents causing a problem to the candidate as well as the officials. The problems of management, storage have been eliminated by using a centralized storage method where all the documents are stored in a server and user will have to carry the documents in a digital format. One time passwords in form of Graphical code makes it more secured. Every transaction is transparent to User and hidden from any external entity. This project stores the document, gets it attested, and makes the retrieval process easier.

II. EXISTING SYSTEM

The idea arises from a problem that has been faced in form of the educational institute since recent years. Procedures get delayed because of the same problem. Also, this is a cost effective enhancement.

There exists difficulty in managing documents physically in an institute with a large no of candidates enroll.

Retrieval of document involves searching in a set of many documents and it is time consuming. Information might be not available all the time to the intended users.

Documents stored in an image format, if not compressed, creates a load on the storage server degrading its performance.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The system has been proposed after an in and out study of traditional method. The system approach transfers the functioning from physical methods to digital ones. The proposed system is flexible, efficient and secured.

This project is a web based application accessible by mobile phones and desktop systems. The process of enrolment has to be done with personal computer and scanner for scanning the documents

Each candidate will be given with a unique identity number. The number will be used by the principal for accessing the documents. The principal will put the digital signature for attestation. The Digital Signature will be generated based on session details

Retrieval of documents is based on dynamically generating the QR in the form of OTP and authenticating the guest users based on session details. The user will require credentials and an OTP, while the guest will require QR generated dynamically by the system.

IV. ADVANTAGES OF PROPOSED SYSTEM

The project is based on functioning of an institute having a need for managing documents. The survey has been conducted in institutes of similar nature as mentioned above. Institutes find it difficult to manage documents and retrieval process needs a search in shelves of documents. The institutes need an inventory house for storing documents, which can be avoided by storing the documents digitally in a server. The documents will be stored in Image format. The images will be compressed to keep the server free from holding overload. The searching process will become easier as the images will be grouped together in folders and indexing will be done. The authenticity of digital documents can be questioned or challenged in some cases, hence the documents would be sent for digital attestation by principal or any verifying officer. The digital signature will be generated based on session details of current session. The digital signature is nothing but a watermark put over the image with some piece of code embedded within. The retrieval process has been made easier for the user as well as the guest. The user gets an OTP for login and the guest gets a QR code. The user scans the QR code and triggers the server for giving document access to the guest. The QR code will be generated based on session details being dynamic in nature. The guest will get access after consent by the user. It will have

the process of selecting the documents before downloading. The retrieval will give access to the concerned person for downloading the images.

Fig 1. Process Diagram

V. CONCLUSION

The proposed system is a solution to document management in an easy way where it is difficult to manage date of multiple people involved in any organization. The system is secure and useful for Human Resource Management.

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